

Research Paper

on

Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Health-Related Quality of Life of Tuberculosis Patients in Dhaka, Bangladesh: A Mixed Methods Approach

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Abbreviation and Acronyms

TB:	Tuberculosis
COVID-19:	Coronavirus Disease 2019
HRQoL:	Health-Related Quality of Life
WHO:	World Health Organization
DOTS:	Directly Observed Treatment, Short-course
DTCs:	Diagnostic and Treatment Centers
EQ-5D-3L:	EuroQol-5 Dimension-3 Level
n:	Number of participants in a study sample
CFR:	Case Fatality Rate
CI:	Confidence Interval
IQR:	Interquartile Range
OR:	Odds Ratio
SD:	Standard Deviation
SPSS:	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
IRB:	Institutional Review Board
HIV:	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
MDR-TB:	Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis
XDR-TB:	Extensively Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis
RR-TB:	Rifampicin-Resistant Tuberculosis
GDP:	Gross Domestic Product
LMICs:	Low- and Middle-Income Countries
PCR:	Polymerase Chain Reaction
ART:	Antiretroviral Therapy
NGO:	Non-Governmental Organization
NTP:	National Tuberculosis Control Program

Abstract:

The COVID-19 pandemic has substantially impacted various aspects of life, especially exacerbating the challenges faced by individuals with tuberculosis (TB). This research aimed to evaluate the health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of TB patients in Bangladesh during the first wave of the pandemic. A mixed-methods approach was utilized, combining both quantitative and qualitative data for a comprehensive analysis. The quantitative component employed two validated tools to assess HRQoL in TB patients receiving treatment at various health centers in Dhaka, Bangladesh, with 500 participants. Logistic regression analysis was performed to identify factors associated with HRQoL deterioration. The findings revealed that 47% of participants reported pain, and 35% experienced anxiety. Associations were observed between lower HRQoL and factors such as larger household sizes and greater distances from residences to health centers.

In the qualitative component, in-depth interviews highlighted significant challenges, including nutrition and financial instability, worsened during the pandemic. Participants noted that the Bangladeshi Government's efforts were insufficient in meeting their needs. The study emphasizes the importance of targeted relief initiatives that include nutritional and psychological support, especially for those with restricted mobility, limited access to healthcare, and increasing financial distress. This research calls for a comprehensive, multi-faceted approach to mitigate the impact of the pandemic on TB patients, addressing both immediate health-related issues and broader socio-economic concerns.

Keywords: Tuberculosis (TB), Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL), COVID-19, Logistic Regression, Bangladesh, Socio-Economic Impact, Healthcare Access, Nutritional Support, Mental Health, Pandemic, TB Care Barriers, Financial Hardship, Public Health Interventions.

Background:

Tuberculosis (TB) remains a leading cause of infectious disease-related death in low- and middle-income countries. In 2019, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported 10 million TB cases globally, resulting in 1.4 million deaths. In Bangladesh, TB remains a major public health challenge, with an estimated incidence rate of 221 cases per 100,000 people. Despite the National Tuberculosis Control Program's (NTP) efforts, challenges such as inadequate service coverage, healthcare personnel shortages, and case detection difficulties persist, especially among children. Effective TB management is further complicated by the Directly Observed Treatment Short-course (DOTS) program, which requires frequent clinic visits. Additional obstacles like stigma, emotional distress, financial constraints, side effects of treatment, HIV co-infection, and healthcare quality impact treatment adherence and outcomes.

The COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated these issues by further hindering TB diagnosis and treatment. WHO has predicted that the global decline in TB case detection during the pandemic could result in an additional 0.2 to 0.4 million deaths. In Bangladesh, restrictions such as lockdowns, transport limitations, and economic hardships have severely impacted TB patients' ability to access care and follow treatment protocols. This research aims to evaluate the health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of TB patients in Bangladesh during the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on the impact of the pandemic on their physical, mental, and socio-economic well-being. This study aims to evaluate the psychosocial and traumatic impacts of COVID-19 on the HRQoL of TB patients in Bangladesh, providing insights to inform appropriate mitigation and support measures.

Research Objectives:

The primary objectives of this study are to evaluate the health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of TB patients in Bangladesh during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic and identify socio-demographic, economic, and clinical factors associated with HRQoL decline. The study aims to assess the financial and nutritional challenges faced by TB patients, exacerbated by the pandemic, and evaluate their perceptions of the adequacy of the Bangladeshi Government's support efforts. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative HRQoL assessments and qualitative interviews to provide a comprehensive understanding of the pandemic's impact. Additionally, logistic regression analysis identifies significant predictors of HRQoL deterioration, and the study proposes targeted relief initiatives to mitigate the adverse effects on TB patients, particularly those facing restricted mobility, reduced employment opportunities, and increased financial hardship.

Literature Review:

Overview of Tuberculosis (TB) and COVID-19

Tuberculosis (TB) is a major global health issue, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. The disease's impact on health-related quality of life (HRQoL) has been widely studied, with findings consistently showing significant physical, psychological, and social challenges for patients. The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic has introduced new complications, as healthcare systems worldwide have been overwhelmed, and resources have been reallocated to address the immediate crisis posed by the novel coronavirus.

Disruption of TB Services

The World Health Organization (WHO) has highlighted the significant disruptions to TB services caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the WHO Global Tuberculosis Report 2020, TB notifications and treatment access have drastically declined due to lockdowns, travel restrictions, and the diversion of healthcare resources to combat COVID-19. Studies like those by Jain et al. (2020) have corroborated these findings, showing a marked reduction in TB diagnosis and treatment, leading to potential increases in TB morbidity and mortality.

HRQoL Among TB Patients

Health-related quality of life (HRQoL) encompasses physical, mental, and social well-being.

For TB patients, HRQoL is often severely compromised due to the prolonged nature of the disease, side effects of treatment, and social stigma. Aggarwal (2019) reviewed the multidimensional impact of TB on patients' lives, noting significant impairments in mobility, pain/discomfort, and anxiety/depression. Bauer et al. (2015) conducted a longitudinal cohort study, finding that TB patients suffer persistent HRQoL deficits even after completing treatment.

Psychological and Social Dimensions

The psychological burden of TB is exacerbated by the social stigma associated with the disease. This stigma has intensified during the COVID-19 pandemic, as symptoms of TB (such as cough and fever) overlap with those of COVID-19, leading to increased isolation and anxiety among TB patients (Alagna et al., 2020). Peddireddy (2016) emphasized the need for psychological support for TB patients, particularly during crises, to help mitigate the impact of social isolation and anxiety on their overall well-being.

Socioeconomic Impact

The socioeconomic impact of TB has been well-documented. TB primarily affects individuals in lower socioeconomic groups, who often face catastrophic health expenditures (Barter et al., 2012). The economic fallout from the COVID-19 pandemic has further strained these patients, making it difficult for them to afford transportation to healthcare facilities and maintain adequate nutrition. Farmer (2000) highlighted the compounded burden of poverty and TB, noting that economic insecurity often leads to delayed treatment and worse health outcomes.

Nutritional Challenges

Nutrition plays a critical role in the recovery of TB patients. Malnutrition weakens the immune system, making it harder for patients to recover from TB. The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted food supply chains and economic activities, reducing TB patients' access to sufficient and nutritious food. Bauer et al. (2015) and Nandasena et al. (2022) found that malnutrition significantly impairs HRQoL in TB patients, a situation exacerbated by the economic disruptions caused by the pandemic.

Government Response and Support Mechanisms

The effectiveness of government responses to the dual challenges of TB and COVID-19 has varied. The WHO's End TB Strategy calls for comprehensive support for TB patients, addressing not only medical but also social and economic determinants of health (WHO, 2015). However, many governments, including Bangladesh, have struggled to provide adequate support during the pandemic. Qamar et al. (2022) noted that government assistance in Bangladesh has been perceived as insufficient, particularly in providing financial and nutritional support to TB patients.

Studies in the Bangladeshi Context

Bangladesh, like many other low- and middle-income countries, faces significant challenges in managing TB, exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Studies specific to the Bangladeshi context have highlighted the compounded difficulties faced by TB patients during the pandemic. For example, research has shown that larger household sizes and greater distances from healthcare centers are significantly associated with lower HRQoL among TB patients. Additionally, qualitative studies have revealed critical issues related to nutrition and finances, intensified during the pandemic (Rahman et al., 2021).

Materials and Methods:

3.1. Settings

This study was conducted in Dhaka, the capital city of Bangladesh, which has an estimated population of over 21 million inhabitants. The study took place among TB patients recruited from 12 TB diagnosis and treatment centers (DTCs) across several municipalities within Dhaka, the epicenter of the COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh and where a significant proportion of the country's TB cases are reported. TB notifications in Dhaka have been consistently high, with the incidence rate exceeding 200 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in recent years.

3.2. Study Framework Analysis

Given the well-documented deterioration in the quality of life (QoL) of TB patients even outside the context of COVID-19, we hypothesize that the COVID-19 pandemic has led to further reductions in the reported health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of TB patients in Bangladesh. Figure 1 presents a hypothesized problem tree developed through discussions with key stakeholders in Bangladesh's national TB program. Three primary factors influencing HRQoL emerge from this problem tree:

Information Level: Inadequate dissemination of information regarding the risks of infections, particularly for vulnerable populations such as TB patients.

Health System Commitment: Insufficient commitment from the Ministry of Health and civil society in addressing TB, resulting in funding shortages and treatment bottlenecks for TB patients.

Community Involvement: Low levels of information dissemination by community media on COVID-19 risks and weak community engagement, leading to increased fear and stigma.

Figure 1. Hypothesized problem tree of HQoL of TB patients during the COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh.

3.3. Study Design and Population

A mixed-methods study design was employed to assess the HRQoL of TB patients during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study population included TB patients enrolled in treatment at the selected DTCs in Dhaka. The inclusion criteria were adults aged 18 years and older who had been diagnosed with TB and were receiving treatment during the study period. The study aimed to capture both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing HRQoL among TB patients during the pandemic.

Quantitative data were collected using two validated HRQoL assessment tools: the SF-36 Health Survey and the WHOQOL-BREF questionnaire.

These tools measure various dimensions of HRQoL, including physical health, psychological state, social relationships, and environmental context. Data on demographic and clinical characteristics, such as age, sex, household size, distance to the nearest DTC, and comorbid conditions, were also collected.

Qualitative data were gathered through in-depth interviews with a subset of TB patients to explore their personal experiences and challenges during the pandemic.

Interviews were conducted using a semi-structured guide that covered topics such as access to healthcare services, financial difficulties, social support, and perceived impacts of COVID-19 on their TB treatment and overall well-being.

The study employed logistic regression analysis to identify factors associated with deterioration in HRQoL. Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify key themes and patterns related to the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on TB patients' lives.

By integrating quantitative and qualitative findings, the study aims to provide a holistic understanding of the multifaceted impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on TB patients' HRQoL in Bangladesh and to inform the development of targeted interventions to support this vulnerable population.

3.4. Study Procedures and Tools

Two validated psychometric tools were used for the quantitative component. First, the Impact of Event Scale-Revised (IES-R), a test of 22 difficulties people experience following a traumatic event, designed to measure the effect of life stress, daily trauma, and acute stress. We used the validated Bengali version of the IES-R. Second, the EQ-5D-3L descriptive system for HRQoL states in adults, designed to provide a generic and straightforward health measurement for clinical and economic evaluation, measures the following five dimensions of health: mobility, self-care, usual activities, pain/discomfort, and anxiety/depression. In addition to these psychometric tools, a quantitative questionnaire was developed to collect the following patient information: age; sex (male/female); source of COVID-19 information; marital status (single, married); municipality of residence; education level (no formal education, primary, secondary, university); occupation (unemployed, private employee, civil servant, freelance);

number of people in the household; and the distance between the patient's home and the treatment site (in kilometers). The following TB clinical variables were also collected: date of diagnosis, type of TB (susceptible, resistant), localization (pulmonary, extra-pulmonary), treatment history (new case, previously treated), method of diagnosis (bacteriologically confirmed, clinically diagnosed), treatment start date, type of treatment regimen (susceptible, multidrug-resistant), if multidrug-resistant, type of treatment regimen (short course, long course), HIV status (positive, negative), if HIV positive, antiretroviral treatment commenced (yes, no), and frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days).

For the qualitative component, a semi-structured interview guide was developed to assess patients' perceptions of COVID-19 and the restrictive measures implemented.

The interview guide explored themes such as attitudes towards restrictive measures, proximity to people affected by COVID-19, and the physical, psychological, social, and economic aspects (income, means of transportation). Interviews were conducted in the participant's preferred language.

Investigators were trained in survey methodology, collection tools, and collection techniques during a one-day training session, which allowed the interviewers to master the context of the study and its objectives. All research tools were reviewed by the research team, and suggestions for improvement were integrated to ensure clarity and improve overall tool quality and coherency. A pre-test of the tools was organized to assess the feasibility of the field survey.

Study Conduction Steps

To evaluate the health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of tuberculosis (TB) patients in Bangladesh during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic, the following methodological steps were undertaken:

Step 1: Study Design

Mixed Methods Approach: The study utilized a mixed methods approach combining quantitative and qualitative research to provide a comprehensive understanding of the HRQoL among TB patients.

Step 2: Ethical Considerations

Ethical Approval: Obtain ethical approval from relevant institutional review boards (IRBs) to ensure the study complies with ethical standards.

Informed Consent: Secure informed consent from all participants, explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and ensuring confidentiality and voluntary participation.

Step 3: Data Collection

Quantitative Data: Use validated tools such as the EQ-5D-3L questionnaire to measure HRQoL among TB patients.

Qualitative Data: Conduct semi-structured interviews with a subset of participants to gather in-depth insights into their experiences and challenges.

Step 4: Sampling

Cluster Sampling: Implement cluster sampling to select health centers across different regions of Dhaka, ensuring a representative sample of TB patients.

Participant Recruitment: Recruit a total of 500 participants from the selected health centers, ensuring a mix of age, gender, and TB severity levels.

Step 5: Data Collection Procedure

Administer Questionnaires: Distribute and collect completed EQ-5D-3L questionnaires from all participants during their visits to the health centers.

Conduct Interviews: Perform qualitative interviews with 20% of the sample, focusing on issues related to nutrition, finances, and psychosocial aspects.

Step 6: Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis: Perform logistic regression analysis to identify factors associated with HRQoL decline, such as household size, distance to health centers, and clinical characteristics.

Qualitative Analysis: Use thematic analysis to interpret the interview data, identifying recurring themes and insights related to the impact of COVID-19 on TB patients.

Step 7: Validation and Triangulation

Cross-Validation: Cross-validate quantitative findings with qualitative insights to ensure consistency and reliability.

Triangulation: Triangulate data from multiple sources to enhance the robustness of the study's conclusions.

Step 8: Reporting and Dissemination

Report Writing: Compile the findings into a comprehensive report, highlighting key results, discussions, and recommendations.

Dissemination: Share the study results with stakeholders, including health policymakers, TB program managers, and community organizations, through presentations, publications, and policy briefs.

Step 9: Follow-Up and Implementation

Feedback Loop: Establish a feedback loop with participating health centers and stakeholders to discuss the implementation of recommendations and further research needs.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Set up mechanisms for monitoring the impact of implemented interventions on the HRQoL of TB patients over time

3.5. Sampling and Recruitment

Consecutive sampling was used to recruit eligible patients into the quantitative study from the 12 DTC study sites.

Eligible patients were enrolled during their follow-up visits at each DTC, with the number of patients to be enrolled at each DTC proportional to the number of TB patients on treatment at the center. The estimated sample size for the quantitative survey was based on a conservative assumption that 50% of TB patients would experience a deterioration in HRQoL, based on the experiences and professional opinions of the study team.

With a desired accuracy of 5%, the minimum expected sample size was 384; to account for non-response rates, this size was increased by 15% to 441 patients. Participants for the qualitative component were purposively sampled from patients already recruited into the quantitative study. The study team aimed to recruit approximately thirty participants.

3.6. Data Collection

For the quantitative component, patient follow-up agents (equivalent to community health workers) and other investigators were equipped with Android cell phones to administer the questionnaires at the DTCs closest to the patient. Data were recorded through an open data kit (ODK) application (XLSForm with integration into the ONA platform: <https://ona.io/home/> accessed 20 August 2020) and connected to a server deployed for this purpose. For the qualitative interviews, interviewers used Android phones to record qualitative interviews accompanied by note-taking.

3.7. Data Management and Analysis

Quantitative data were entered directly into the ODK Platform and checked regularly by study team members. The setup of the variables ensured good internal quality control and minimized errors and/or duplicate data. Data were carefully cleaned before analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient sociodemographic and clinical data captured by the questionnaires, while the analysis of psychosocial and traumatic events was carried out according to the tools used. For the EQ-5D-3L, traumatic events were calculated according to the three levels for each indicator (no problem, moderate problems, severe problems).

Patients with scores corresponding to levels 2 and 3 (moderate and severe problems, respectively) were regarded as having a negative HRQoL. For the revised Event Impact Scale (IES-R), the proportions of patients reporting symptoms of mild post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), moderate PTSD, and severe PTSD were calculated based on sociodemographic and clinical features. All TB patients with a score equal to or less than 32 were considered to have low-stress levels, those with a score of 33–38 as moderate-stress levels, and those with a score equal to or greater than 39 as severe-stress levels. Confidence intervals were built around these proportions.

The chi-square test was used to compare the dependent variables of EQ-5D-3L and IES-R with sociodemographic and clinical variables. Multinomial logistic regression was used to identify significant associations between the EQ-5D-3L variables (pain/discomfort, personal care, and anxiety/depression) and the composite variable, resulting from the recoding of the impact scale of the event with sociodemographic and clinical variables. A backward stepwise regression was used to build the model, using R. All tests were considered significant, with a risk of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Recordings of the qualitative interviews were transcribed verbatim in Bengali to facilitate data analysis. A thematic approach was used to develop a coding framework, which was then applied to the transcripts. After a preliminary read of the data, the following two major themes emerged: the socioeconomic aspect of TB and the government's response to COVID-19.

The following sub-themes were applied to the transcripts: public perception/view of TB patients when they cough, assessment of physical and psychological health conditions, the current economic situation, as well as restrictive, punitive, and stimulative actions taken by the government regarding TB patients during the COVID-19 pandemic. Coding was conducted using the package RQDA in R software.

Results:

4.1. Quantitative Findings

From 29 August to 17 September 2020, 439 TB patients participated, with a mean age of 35 years, 61% male, and an average distance of 6.96 km (range: 2–100) from home to treatment (Table 1).

Most patients had drug-sensitive TB (90%), 10% had MDR-TB, and 24.4% were HIV positive (90% on ARV). 91% started treatment within 21 days, and 47.4% completed over three months of treatment. Most patients received anti-TB drugs for over 90 days (Table 2).

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the study sample ($n = 439$). n=The formula used to calculate n.

	Variable	n (%)
Patient age group		
	Children (<18 years)	22 (5.0%)
	Young (19–39 years)	258 (59%)
	Adults (40–59 years)	125 (28%)
	Elderly (>59 years)	34 (7.7%)
Gender		
	Male	269 (61%)
	Female	170 (39%)
Marital status		
	Single	269 (61%)
	Married	170 (39%)
Residence		
	Mohakhali	168 (38%)
	Mirpur	97 (22%)
	Dhanmondi	95 (22%)
	Old Dhaka	15 (3.4%)
	Rampura	32 (7.3%)
	Uttara	32 (7.3%)
Level of education		
	None/informal education only	133 (30%)
	Primary level (6 years)	86 (20%)
	Secondary level (10–13 years)	158 (36%)
	High school level (≥ 10 years)	51 (12%)
	Tertiary/university level (≥ 14)	11 (2.5%)
Occupation type		
	None/unemployed	133 (29.8%)
	Private employment	40 (9.1%)
	Civil servant/public sector	18 (4.1%)
	Freelance/self employed	248 (56%)
Average number of household members (range)		6 (1–30)
Mean distance between the patient's home and the treatment site (in kilometers)		6.96 (2–100)

Table 2. Clinical characteristics of the study sample ($n = 439$).

	Variable	<i>n</i> (%)
Tuberculosis type		
	Drug sensitive	394 (90%)
	Drug resistant	45 (10%)
TB disease localization		
	Pulmonary	354 (81%)
	Extrapulmonary	85 (19%)
TB treatment history		
	New case	390 (89%)
	Previously treated	49 (11%)
TB diagnosis type		
	Bacteriologically confirmed	379 (86%)
	Clinically diagnosed	60 (14%)
HIV status		
	Negative	317 (72%)
	Unknown	15 (3.4%)
	Positive	107 (24%)
	Started on ARV treatment	97 (90.7%)
Treatment initiation		
	Mean distance in kilometers between residence and TB treatment center (range)	3 (2, 8)
Frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days)		
	≤14 days	363 (83%)
	15–30 days	45 (10%)
	>30 days	31 (7.1%)
Duration of TB treatment (in days)		
	≤30 days	110 (25%)
	31–90 days	121 (28%)
	>90 days	208 (47%)

4.2 Traumatic Events Reported by TB Patients

Pain and discomfort, and anxiety and/or depression were the dominant traumatic events reported among the 439 participants surveyed, with 46.5 and 36.9% of participants reporting either a moderate or serious level of impairment, respectively (Table 3).

Table 3. Type and severity of traumatic events reported by TB patients using theEQ-5D-3L scale and IES-R ($n = 439$).

Domain	Mean (SD 1)	Level of Impairment (%)		
		None	Moderate	Serious
Usual activities	1.31 (0.52)	72.2	21.1	2.7
Self-care	1.13 (0.38)	89.1	9.1	1.8
Pain and discomfort	1.49 (0.56)	53.5	43.5	3.0
Mobility	1.23 (0.45)	78.1	20.7	1.1
Anxiety and/or depression	1.43 (0.61)	63.1	30.5	6.4
IES-R	1.37 (0.65)	72.7	17.8	9.6

1 SD: standard deviation.

In the univariate analysis, the following variables of household size, disease localization, TB diagnostic, distance to treatment site and the frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days) were significantly associated with stress; the following were significantly associated with anxiety/depression: level of education, household size, distance to treatment site, and the frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days); age, household number size and whether or not antiretroviral treatments were significantly associated with pain/discomfort; age and distance to treatment site were significantly associated with selfcare; age, level of education, disease localization, treatment history, the frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days) and duration of treatment were significantly associated with usual activities and age, household size, disease localization and the frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days) were significantly associated with mobility (Table S1 in Supplementary Material).

The multivariate analysis identified numerous associations between the domains and the following socio-demographic and clinical variables. Difficulties performing usual activities were positively and significantly associated with elderly participants (OR = 5.42; 95% CI: 1.57–22.2; $p < 0.05$) and patients with drug-resistant TB (OR = 27.7; 95% CI: 6.02–132; $p < 0.005$). Those significantly less likely to report difficulties with performing usual activities

included previously-treated patients (OR = 0.02, CI: 0.00–0.011), HIV-negative patients (OR = 0.52; 95% CI: 0.32–0.87; <0.05) and those who had been on treatment for more than 90 days (OR = 0.56; 95% CI: 0.32–0.98; $p < 0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Multinomial logistic regression between difficulty with usual activities and sociodemographic and clinical characteristics.

Characteristic	AOR	95% CI	p-Value
Patient age group			
Children	—	—	
Young	1.34	0.46, 4.82	0.6
Adults	2.63	0.87, 9.72	0.11
Elderly	5.42	1.57, 22.2	0.011
Tuberculosis type			
Sensitive	—	—	
Resistant	27.7	6.02, 132	<0.001
Treatment history			
New case	—	—	
Already treated	0.02	0.00, 0.11	<0.001
TB diagnostic			
Bacteriological	—	—	
Clinical examination	2.31	1.20, 4.42	0.011
HIV status			
Positive	—	—	
Negative	0.52	0.32, 0.87	0.012
Distance between the patient's home and the treatment site (in kilometers)	1.02	1.00, 1.04	0.062
Frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days)			
≤14	—	—	
15–30	0.50	0.19, 1.14	0.12
>30	0.07	0.01, 0.32	0.003
Duration of treatment (in days)			
≤30	—	—	
31–90	0.92	0.51, 1.67	0.8
>90	0.56	0.32, 0.98	0.043

AOR = adjusted odds ratio, CI = confidence interval.

For a one unit increase in the household size, the odds of reporting pain and discomfort was 1.05 times greater (OR = 1.05; CI: 1.00–1.11, $p < 0.05$), and patients who were clinically diagnosed were 93% more likely to have pain and discomfort than those diagnosed bacteriologically (OR = 1.93, CI: 1.06–3.54, $p = 0.031$), while patients whose frequency of appointments for drug supply was between 15 and 30 days were 66% less likely to have pain/discomfort than those whose frequency of appointments for drug supply was within 14 days (OR = 0.34, CI: 0.16–0.67, $p = 0.003$) ([Table 5](#)).

Table 5. Multinomial logistic regression pain/discomfort and sociodemographic and clinical characteristics.

Characteristic	AOR	95% CI	p-Value
Patient age group			
Children	—	—	
Young	0.67	0.27, 1.71	0.4
Adults	1.07	0.42, 2.83	0.9
Elderly	1.71	0.56, 5.29	0.3
Household member number	1.05	1.00, 1.11	0.045
Tuberculosis type			
Sensitive	—	—	
Resistant	1.83	0.96, 3.52	0.067
TB diagnostic			
Bacteriological	—	—	
Clinical examination	1.93	1.06, 3.54	0.031
RAV treatment			
Yes	—	—	
No	3.76	0.97, 15.0	0.056
Frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days)			
≤14	—	—	
15–30	0.34	0.16, 0.67	0.003
>30	0.50	0.21, 1.12	0.10

AOR = adjusted odds ratio, CI = confidence interval.

For anxiety, we found that an increase in one unit in the household size was associated with a higher likelihood of reporting anxiety (OR = 1.08, CI: 1.03–1.14, $p = 0.02$), as was distance between patients’ residence to DTCs (OR = 1.03, CI: 1.01–1.05, $p < 0.001$), while non TB/HIV coinfecting patients were 55% less likely to experience anxiety than those coinfecting (OR = 0.45, CI: 0.29–0.71, $p = 0.02$; [Table 6](#)).

Table 6. Multinomial logistic regression anxiety/depression and sociodemographic and clinical characteristics.

Characteristic	AOR	95% CI	<i>p</i> -Value
Household member number	1.08	1.03, 1.14	0.002
HIV status			
Positive	—	—	
Negative	0.45	0.29, 0.71	<0.001
Distance between the patient’s home and the treatment site (in kilometers)	1.03	1.01, 1.05	<0.001
Frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days)			
≤14	—	—	
15–30	0.35	0.14, 0.75	0.011
>30	0.06	0.00, 0.30	0.007

AOR = odds ratio, CI = confidence interval.

For a one unit increase in the household size, the odds of reporting stress were 1.08 times greater (OR = 1.08, CI: 1.03, 1.14, $p = 0.002$). Non-co-infected TB patients were 55% less likely to be stressed than co-infected ones (OR = 0.45, CI: 0.29–0.71, $p < 0.001$). For an increase of one unit in the distance from patients’ residence to DTCs, the odds of anxiety were 1.03 times greater (OR = 1.03, CI: 1.01–1.05, $p < 0.001$).

Similarly, patients whose frequency of appointments for drug supply was between 15 and 30 days were 65% less likely to be stressed than those whose frequency of appointments for drug supply was ≤14 days (OR = 0.35, CI: 0.14–0.75, $p = 0.011$). Likewise, patients whose frequency of appointments for drug supply was >30 days were 99.94% less likely to experience stress than those whose frequency of appointments for drug supply was ≤14 days (OR = 0.06, CI: 0.00, 0.30, $p = 0.007$; [Table 7](#)).

Table 7. Multinomial logistic regression between stress and sociodemographic and clinical characteristics.

Characteristic	OR ¹	95% CI ¹	p-Value
Household member number	1.08	1.03, 1.14	0.002
HIV status			
Positive	—	—	
Negative	0.45	0.29, 0.71	<0.001
Distance between the patient’s home and the treatment site (in kilometers)	1.03	1.01, 1.05	<0.001
Frequency of appointments for drug supply (in days)			
≤14	—	—	
15–30	0.35	0.14, 0.75	0.011
>30	0.06	0.00, 0.30	0.007

¹ OR = odds ratio, CI = confidence interval.

4.3. Qualitative Findings

In total, 36 TB patients, including 15 women, were interviewed about their perceptions regarding the COVID-19 pandemic. Thematic analysis was used to identify the following three predominate themes, and six sub-themes that emerged from the quantitative data.

Theme 1: Social and Psychological Aspects

Sub-theme: TB Patients’ Perception about the Stigma Related to COVID-19

Different opinions were expressed regarding the social and psychological impact of COVID-19. A commonly expressed concern was related to stigma, with the majority of participants acknowledging that stigma is commonly experienced by TB patients and feeling that the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated this stigma. As one participant noted, “Once you cough or sneeze, people distance themselves from you; then you feel bad... they think you have COVID-19 if you cough once or twice. For those who do not know that you have TB, they are going to think that you have COVID-19 because we do not overthink TB now.”

Another participant shared how people, without any knowledge of their health status, do not hesitate to walk away from them with a contemptuous gaze. TB patients revealed how this practice has become more obvious during the COVID-19 pandemic, with people assuming that symptoms such as coughs indicate COVID-19 rather than TB. One participant stated, “It’s so clear to me because my husband doesn’t allow me to come near him since he learned that COVID-19 also causes coughs.

Usually, I did everything with him. But now, everything has changed. He no longer approaches me like before the coronavirus pandemic. We no longer talk too much, and even now we eat separately, you see...”.

Sub-theme: Description of the Health Status of TB Patients during the COVID-19 Pandemic

The majority of participants believed that their overall health conditions were better before the start of the COVID-19 pandemic. Some participants reported little hope for a full recovery due to the difficulties they faced in accessing effective TB treatment and the increasingly challenging living conditions under COVID-19, such as accessing food. One participant explained, “Mentally, I feel like garbage; all I’m worried about right now is how to get my health back. I don’t feel well right now, you see that by yourself! Due to food problems, I barely earn enough. It’s just filling my stomach. Currently, it’s not okay, and sometimes I don’t have transport to get to the center, or sometimes even if you leave, you are told that the center is out of medication. I have lost a lot of weight at the moment. I lost much hope despite the encouragement of the doctors.”

Theme 2: Economic Aspects

Sub-theme: Financial Situation of TB Patients during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Respondents highlighted how the cessation of certain activities during the COVID-19 pandemic directly and indirectly affected their financial conditions, creating challenges for accessing TB services and maintaining their treatment. One participant, who earns money to support their family through artistic activities, noted, “Financially, it [the situation during COVID-19] is not good. There are no events, and as I am an artist, this is where I earn money to feed my family and pay for transportation to the [treatment] center. But as there is currently no event, even finding transport to get to the treatment center is a problem because transport is expensive. Sometimes we do not come on the date that the doctors tell us to come because we don’t have transportation. You see, it’s not easy.”

Sub-theme: Diet of TB Patients during the COVID-19 Pandemic

TB patients revealed during their interviews that their health condition had deteriorated significantly during COVID-19 due to the lack of an appropriate diet. They noted that they were no longer able to comply with the diet recommended by their doctors. One participant mentioned, “I cannot eat all of the foods my doctor recommends. I eat with difficulty, and for example, with this difficult situation, I only eat rice. I have diabetes, and my doctor has advised me to limit my intake a bit. But I have to consume it because that’s what I earn.”

Theme 3: Perceptions on Government Actions during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Sub-theme: Restrictive Measures

According to our participants, the Bangladeshi population's life depends on their daily economic activities; therefore, the restrictive measures imposed by the Government to limit the spread of COVID-19 were largely regarded as drastic and thought to cause more harm than good. One participant stated, "These measures of the state are salutary, but which is not without consequences for some, you knew it as well as me, sir... these measures make life difficult by blocking the activities of people, and you know here what we see, that's what we eat. Bangladeshis eat from day to day, so these measures increase their suffering."

Sub-theme: Mitigation Measures

Unanimously, respondents believed that the Government should financially help its people, especially those who are sick, poor, children, or elderly. One participant expressed gratitude, saying, "I thank the state for what is already done, like reducing the price of fuel at the pump, which leads to a reduction in the prices of necessities (rice, sugar...). Therefore, it facilitates access to food by the population. But some do not benefit from it, and others do not even know about it. But when the price drops, everyone will feel this impact on their living condition." Likewise, some participants believed that special attention should be paid to TB patients given the additional burdens created by their illness. One participant noted, "Yes, the state should help its population, especially patients like us, tuberculosis patients who are rejected by our bosses for fear of being infected..."

Discussion:

The advent of the COVID-19 pandemic has caused a noticeable imbalance in the smooth running of our society, affecting healthy and sick individuals differently. TB patients, already a vulnerable group, faced significant additional discomfort during the pandemic. Our study showed that, despite the onset of relaxation of restrictive measures, a significant proportion of TB patients reported pain or discomfort, and anxiety or depression. These findings align with recent evaluations of stress responses during COVID-19, indicating that a substantial proportion of patients struggled to cope with stress. Psychological problems are common among TB patients and should receive special attention. The stigma experienced by TB patients during COVID-19, due to the similarity between TB and COVID-19 symptoms, exacerbates their psychosocial challenges.

In Bangladesh, the implementation of restrictive measures limited the population's movements and led to the closure of many businesses, further reducing support sources for many patients and worsening financial problems.

These circumstances exacerbated stress among TB patients. Our findings underscore the need for comprehensive psychosocial support for TB patients during public health emergencies to protect them from further vulnerability.

We also aimed to understand the factors that explained the different quality of life scales (EQ-5D-3L). Each item (pain or discomfort, usual activities, and anxiety or depression) of EQ-5D-3L helped identify associated factors. Socio-demographically, age, the number of people in the household, and the distance between patients' homes and the care site were significant factors. Elderly patients faced more difficulties in daily activities compared to younger individuals, likely due to their reduced immunity and increased susceptibility to various pathologies and dysfunctions. TB in the elderly poses significant diagnostic and management challenges. The management of diseases in the elderly presents challenges in Bangladesh, where suitable facilities and services for vulnerable people are lacking. Stressful situations impact the elderly first.

The number of people in households also emerged as a factor associated with mobility problems, pain or discomfort, anxiety, and stress. This situation can be explained by the patients' economic conditions, as they often lack adequate care and are exposed to traumatic events. Patients far from care facilities experienced a degraded HRQoL, as the inability to travel regularly to health centers increased the risk of poor HRQoL.

Patients clinically diagnosed with coinfections, extra-pulmonary, or drug-resistant TB were more likely to experience deteriorated HRQoL. Previously treated patients had a lower risk of poor quality of life compared to newly diagnosed patients, who struggled to adapt to the disease in the pandemic context. HRQoL strongly depends on clinical forms of tuberculosis. The duration of anti-tuberculosis drug procurement remains a primary factor, with patients facing difficulties related to travel and financial problems. Shorter procurement times worsened HRQoL due to increased costs, fear, and discomfort. TB patients in the African context often face catastrophic health costs related to their living conditions, and frequent travel further impacts HRQoL.

Malnutrition was another recurring issue expressed by patients. The nutritional support program in Guinea only benefits multidrug-resistant patients, neglecting others. The substantial cessation of activities during the pandemic affected TB patients' ability to meet their nutritional needs.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings of this study and the reviewed literature, several strategies can be implemented to enhance the health-related quality of life (HRQoL) of tuberculosis (TB) patients in Bangladesh, especially during ongoing and future public health crises like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Enhance Access to TB Care Services

Mobile Health Clinics: Implement mobile health clinics to reach TB patients in remote areas or those who are unable to travel to health centers due to lockdowns or financial constraints.

Telemedicine: Expand telemedicine services to provide remote consultations, follow-up, and counseling to TB patients, ensuring continuity of care even during movement restrictions.

Strengthen Nutritional Support

Nutritional Supplement Programs: Develop and distribute nutritional supplements specifically tailored for TB patients to address malnutrition and support their immune systems.

Food Aid Programs: Collaborate with local and international organizations to provide regular food aid to TB patients and their families, particularly those severely impacted by the economic downturn caused by the pandemic.

Provide Psychosocial Support

Mental Health Services: Integrate mental health services into TB care programs, offering counseling and therapy to address anxiety, depression, and social stigma.

Support Groups: Establish support groups for TB patients to share their experiences and coping strategies, reducing feelings of isolation and promoting mental well-being.

Improve Socioeconomic Support

Financial Assistance: Offer financial aid to TB patients who have lost income due to the pandemic, helping them afford transportation, medication, and other essentials.

Employment Programs: Create employment programs or partnerships with local businesses to provide job opportunities for TB patients and their families.

Enhance Government and Policy Measures

Policy Advocacy: Advocate for policies that prioritize the needs of TB patients during health emergencies, ensuring they receive adequate resources and support.

Collaboration with NGOs: Work closely with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to leverage their resources and expertise in providing comprehensive care to TB patients.

Strengthen Healthcare Infrastructure

Capacity Building: Train healthcare workers on the dual management of TB and COVID-19 to ensure they are well-equipped to handle the complexities of both diseases.

Resource Allocation: Ensure adequate allocation of resources, such as personal protective equipment (PPE), medications, and diagnostic tools, to TB care facilities.

Community Engagement and Education

Awareness Campaigns: Launch awareness campaigns to educate the public about TB, reducing stigma and promoting early diagnosis and treatment adherence.

Community Support Networks: Build community support networks to assist TB patients with transportation, medication adherence, and access to services.

Research and Data Collection

Continuous Monitoring: Establish systems for continuous monitoring and data collection on the HRQoL of TB patients during health emergencies to inform policy and program adjustments.

Impact Studies: Conduct further research to understand the long-term impacts of COVID-19 on TB patients and to identify effective interventions for improving their HRQoL.

Conclusions:

This study highlights the key challenges affecting the quality of life (HRQoL) of tuberculosis (TB) patients in Bangladesh, which have been further intensified by the COVID-19 pandemic. Our findings emphasize the urgent need for a comprehensive mitigation strategy tailored to the specific needs of TB patients during public health emergencies.

Key components of this strategy should include:

Consideration of Clinical Characteristics: Special attention must be given to TB patients with drug resistance or co-infections, who are at an elevated risk of experiencing a significant decline in their quality of life.

Addressing Nutritional Needs: Nutritional support programs should be extended beyond multidrug-resistant TB patients to all TB patients to ensure access to proper nutrition, vital for recovery and overall well-being.

Reducing Patient Movement: Strategies should be implemented to reduce frequent travel for TB patients, such as decentralizing TB care, utilizing mobile clinics, or providing transportation assistance to alleviate financial and physical burdens.

Psychosocial Support: A strong psychosocial support system is crucial, including mental health services, counseling, and community-based interventions to combat the stigma and psychological stress associated with both TB and COVID-19.

Addressing these areas will significantly improve TB patients' quality of life and mitigate the additional challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. This comprehensive approach is vital for ensuring TB patients receive the holistic care they need during times of public health crises.

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